

KEY APPROACHES TO EFFICIENT CRIMINAL ASSET RECOVERY

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the analysis of approaches to efficient criminal asset recovery. It was justified practical necessity this process of development of legal framework, institutional capacity, enhancing international cooperation and implementation of innovative approaches, mainly by digitalization activity. Based on the analysis, scientifically substantiated proposals for improving national legislation and law enforcement practice in this sphere have been developed.

Keywords: criminal assets, legal framework, development of policy and strategies, challenges, confiscation and distribution of confiscated assets, international cooperation.

Аннотация: мазкур мақола жиноий активларни қайтаришнинг самарадорли таҳлини таъминлашга хизмат қилувчи муҳим ёндашувлар таҳлиliga бағишланган. Ушбу жараёнда хусусан, норматив-ҳуқуқий асосларни, институционал салоҳиятни такомиллаштириш, халқаро ҳамкорликни кучайтириш ва инновацион ёндашувларни жорий этиш, жумладан, фаолиятни рақамлаштиришнинг амалий аҳамияти асослантириб берилди. Мазкур таҳлил асосида соҳага доир миллий қонунчилик ва ҳуқуқни қўллаш амалиётини такомиллаштиришга доир бир қатор илмий асослантирилган таклифлар ишлаб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: жиноий активлар, қонунчилик базаси, сиёсат ва стратегияларни ишлаб чиқиш, муаммолар, мусодара қилинган мол-мулкни мусодара қилиш ва тақсимлаш, халқаро ҳамкорлик.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена анализу ключевых подходов к эффективному возврату преступных активов. В частности, обоснована практическая значимость развития правовой базы, институционального потенциала, усиления международного сотрудничества и внедрения инновационных подходов, в частности путем цифровизации деятельности. На основе анализа разработаны научно обоснованные предложения по совершенствованию национального законодательства и правоприменительной практики в этой сфере.

Ключевые слова: преступные активы, правовая база, разработка политики и стратегий, вызовы, конфискация и распределение конфискованных активов, международное сотрудничество.

Organised and serious crime continues to represent a significant threat to the rule of law, as well as to the safety and security of societies, both nationally and globally. The value of assets created by illegal activities seems to be substantial. As, according to the UNODC, the cross-border flow of the global proceeds from criminal activities, corruption, and tax evasion is estimated at between \$1 trillion and \$1.6 trillion per year .

This highlights the essential need and practical significance of implementing the appropriate strategies for effective asset recovery. The most efficient strategy for combating organized crime involves targeting the financial resources of criminals, particularly with complex asset recovery measures and systematic approach. Properly chosen approaches and strategies allow law enforcement authorities to identify, seize, and repurpose criminal assets, which significantly hinders the ability of these groups to operate and expand their influence. Moreover, no less importantly, it facilitates the compensation of crime victims, it facilitates the compensation of crime victims, thereby fostering social cohesion and ensuring justice.

The effectiveness of asset recovery operations, which are crucial for enforcing justice and ensuring economic integrity, is influenced by a variety of factors. Among these, the development appropriate policy plays a central role, as proper policy will put in place key legislative and institutional structures that will facilitate the recovery of assets.

In accordance to Article 51 of United Nations Convention against corruption, the return of assets pursuant to this chapter is a fundamental principle of this Convention, and States Parties shall afford one another the widest measure of cooperation and assistance in this regard .

Thus, complete implementation of this provision, mainly depends on policy and strategies executed in member countries. As a well-crafted policy could play a pivotal role in highlighting the significance of asset recovery as a key component of broader anti-corruption initiatives both for achievement national objectives, targets and full commitment of international collaboration. It would strengthen the capacity of competent authorities dealing with asset recovery issues by equipping them with the necessary resources, expertise, and authority to effectively trace, seize, confiscate, and repatriate stolen assets. Furthermore, it would encourage comprehensive international cooperation, ensuring that countries are better positioned to assist one another in recovering illicit assets and combatting global corruption.

The FATF now requires countries to establish asset recovery as a priority, both at the domestic and international levels, and to periodically review their confiscation policies and operational frameworks. Countries must coordinate and share information internally, to identify criminal property. This will bring about the cultural shift to mainstream asset recovery in crime-fighting and focus on asset recovery at the onset of investigations .

This recommendation shall have a significant step in enhancing global efforts to combat financial crime by prioritizing asset recovery. This policy shift aims not only to disrupt the illicit financial flows that fuel organized crime, corruption, and terrorism but also to provide an incentive for countries to take a more proactive stance in the identification, seizure, and confiscation of criminal assets.

A strong and effective legislative framework is crucial for asset recovery as it provides the legal basis and structure necessary to facilitate the recovery of stolen or unlawfully obtained assets.

International regulatory frameworks, such as the UNCAC state that to enable effective asset recovery it is essential that countries establish sound legal and regulatory frameworks. Such regulatory frameworks should oblige financial, professional and other institutions to introduce systems to ensure that there is proper identification of their clients and that all suspicious financial activity is reported in a timely fashion, among others .

Many asset recovery cases involve multiple jurisdictions. A legislative framework allows for international cooperation between countries, providing the legal mechanisms for mutual legal assistance. International conventions, including United Nations Convention Against Corruption (UNCAC), United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC), the OECD Anti-Bribery Convention, and the European Union Asset Recovery and Confiscation Directive provide internationally recognized legal standards and frameworks that countries can adopt or integrate into their domestic legislation.

Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan regulates some issues related to providing legal assistance in criminal matters. Particularly Chapter 64 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for the basic provisions on the procedure for interaction between courts, prosecutors, investigators and inquiry bodies with the competent authorities of foreign states.

In accordance with Article 592 of the Criminal Procedure Code, if it is necessary to carry out procedural actions provided for by this Code on the

territory of a foreign state, the court, prosecutor, investigator, or inquiry officer shall submit a request for their execution by the competent authority of the foreign state in accordance with international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan or on the basis of the principle of reciprocity .

The Criminal Procedure Code prescribes provisions related to authority of competent agencies related to sending requests for legal assistance in criminal matters, requirements on form and content of request for legal assistance in criminal matters, regulations on legal force of evidence obtained on the territory of a foreign state, procedures of execution of requests of foreign countries, as well as on summoning a witness, victim, expert, civil plaintiff, civil defendant, their representatives located outside the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, provisions on forwarding criminal case materials to the competent authority of a foreign state for further investigation, norm on execution of a request for criminal prosecution in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Meanwhile, the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not establish separate provisions and requirements regarding the return of criminal assets from foreign jurisdictions. Particularly in national legislation of Uzbekistan, is not regulated the basis and procedures for recognizing and enforcing decisions of courts of foreign countries on conviction based and non-conviction based recovery of assets; lack of detailed mechanisms for confiscation and distribution of confiscated assets, which may lead to legal disputes and uncertainty.

Legislative challenges related to asset recovery can significantly hinder the effective fight against corruption and money laundering. Uzbekistan is making significant efforts to enhance its legal framework and strengthen measures against corruption and money laundering, particularly in recent years, Uzbekistan has introduced several laws aimed at combating money laundering, such as the law on preventing the legalization of criminal proceeds, and has strengthened oversight of financial transactions.

Along with this, Uzbekistan is actively involved in global initiatives, including cooperation with the Financial Action Task Force (FATF), which supports the implementation of international standards and facilitates asset recovery efforts. General Prosecutor's office of the Republic of Uzbekistan productively cooperates with STAR initiative, as well as, actively participates in the work of UNODC Global Operational Network of Anti-Corruption Law Enforcement Authorities.

The GlobE Network is a rapidly expanding global community of practitioners dedicated to countering corruption, which facilitates transnational cooperation in corruption cases. By facilitating international cooperation between practitioners in cases, and the sharing of knowledge and resources, the GlobE Network aims to strengthen the global response to corruption by enabling law enforcement authorities to detect, investigate and prosecute cross-border corruption offences .

Despite significant efforts taken in Uzbekistan, asset recovery remain deeply complex and multifaceted challenges, requiring continuous improvements in legal frameworks to address emerging threats and fostering deeper and more coordinated international cooperation.

Institutional framework is one of the major factors determining the effectiveness of activities in the field of asset recovery. Institutional capacity refers to the resources, expertise, and technical tools available to agencies responsible for asset recovery. Success is closely related to the existence of specialized offices or departments that focus on the recovery of assets. Such units should be properly resourced, have proper expertise and training, and have access to relevant databases, registries, and financial information to allow practitioners to identify, locate, and freeze assets. They should also have authority to cooperate with foreign authorities with similar mandates (which could include FIUs, law enforcement, and judicial authorities), and to provide upon request technical assistance in “following the money” to third party countries.

By national legislation of Uzbekistan, it has not been directly established coordinating or specialized authority on all objects of recovery of assets. The effectiveness of asset recovery activities in any jurisdiction depends not only on the existence of specialized bodies but also on the capacity and resources available to these institutions. In Uzbekistan, the absence of a single coordinating authority for asset recovery could lead to fragmentation, where different might be involved in various aspects of asset tracing, freezing, and repatriation. Thus, without a single authority responsible for coordinating these efforts, there is a risk of inefficiencies, duplication of efforts, and lack of clear strategic direction.

In this regard, taking into consideration that General Prosecutor’s Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan is national coordinating authority for issues related to providing mutual legal assistance in criminal matters, it is proposed to set as a coordinating authority on asset recovery and for effective implementing this

function, it is proposed to establish separate department focusing only to issues related to asset recovery.

One of the core challenges related to asset recovery in Uzbekistan is ensuring that institutions responsible for identifying, freezing, and repatriating assets are well-resourced and sufficiently trained. Asset recovery requires specialized knowledge and technical tools, such as access to international financial databases, specialized software for tracking illicit flows, and expertise in financial forensics. Additionally, these institutions must have access to high-quality financial and corporate data, including access to beneficial ownership information, which is crucial for tracing assets.

Effective International Cooperation as an Important Component for Asset Recovery. International cooperation allows for the sharing of vital information and resources among law enforcement agencies, financial intelligence units (FIUs), and other relevant authorities.

As recommended by STAR, national institutional frameworks should be set up to ensure that foreign authorities are able to obtain all relevant information on the proceeds of corruption in a timely manner and to enable prompt legal action in response to foreign requests. Such institutional frameworks include encourage upstream contacts with foreign counterparts particularly before the presentation of mutual legal assistance request; establishing focal points of contact for law enforcement and clear and effective channels for mutual legal assistance requests related to corruption and asset recovery; working with existing networks (policy or operational), such as UNCAC, Interpol/StAR, the International Corruption Hunters Alliance, CARIN, and the meeting of law enforcement authorities at the OECD, amongst others, to identify possible gaps and identify best course .

Effective international cooperation is indispensable for successful asset recovery in today's increasingly interconnected world. As crimes, particularly transnational organized crimes, corruption, economic crimes become increasingly complex and global in nature, the need for collaborative efforts between countries, institutions—whether through multilateral agreements, legal frameworks, or technological tool— is the key to overcoming the complex challenges of tracing, freezing, and repatriating illicit assets.

In conclusion, the effective recovery of criminal assets requires a multifaceted approach involving strong legal frameworks, robust institutional capacities, and enhanced international cooperation. For implementing effective asset recovery in Uzbekistan it is required to implement complex of measures in

improvement of legal and regulatory structures, instructional framework, further strengthening and expanding international cooperation. Key element in this regard is the need for greater alignment with international standards such as the UNCAC and the FATF recommendations. By prioritizing asset recovery, enhancing institutional capabilities, and fostering transnational collaboration, countries can better combat organized crime, promote justice for victims, and disrupt the illicit financial networks that undermine global security and economic stability.

